

Research

3D mineralization modeling and mineral resource estimation of the CMA-North prospect (Yaoure gold project, Côte d'Ivoire)

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Abstract: Objective: The aim of this study is to model the mineralization and estimate the mineral resources of the CMA-North prospect of the Yaoure gold project, in order to understand the reality of the subsurface and the mineral potential of the prospect. To achieve this objective, a drilling campaign was carried out, following which data were collected and compiled in a database.

Methodology: The first step consisted of modelling the cross-sections of the 119 drill holes, then digitizing the mineralized zones and finally triangularization was used to construct the 3D solids of the mineralization on the basis of a cut-off grade of 0.4 g/t imposed for the present study. Subsequently, the resource estimate was carried out using several statistical analyses and the block model, which allowed the deposit to be divided into several blocks. On these blocks were applied the inverse distance weighting method which was verified by comparison with the nearest neighbor method.

Results: The mineralization model of the CMA-Nord prospect has mainly a North-South orientation for both oxide and sulphide. It appears in a lenticular form, more visible with the sulphide and plunging towards the east. Resources were estimated and classified according to the constraints applied to the solid blocks. Resources were estimated using the 0.4 g/t cut-off grade imposed for this study; final block models were used for estimation and resources were calculated by material type (oxidized and sulphide). The results showed that on the CMA-North prospect, the mineralization is mainly in the sulphide zone and it is oriented North-South. The block model was used to estimate the mineral resources. The geostatistical method of inverse weighting was applied to this block model and verified by comparison with the nearest neighbor method.

Conclusion: The construction of wireframes by digitizing and triangularizing the zones of importance allowed the establishment of the mineralization model. This model shows that the mineralization has a north-south extension and a large thickness of the envelope of the sulphide mineralization compared to the oxide mineralization.

Keywords: Modeling, estimation, gold resources, Yaoure.

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Introduction

Geology, the science that studies the origin, history, constitution, physical aspects, and development of the Earth, is a complex field where specialists must integrate knowledge of several processes that operate in a three-dimensional

universe. Geologists have been working for many years on mapping the Earth's surface to create geologic maps that can be used for any geologic work or study [25,32]. These maps, created through fieldwork and interpretation of collected data, typically represent the geology of the Earth's surface and serve as a guide for future work. Three-dimensional representations, commonly referred to as 3D models, are becoming increasingly popular among researchers, government agencies, and the geoscience industry [2,31]. Geological modeling can be defined as the set of mathematical methods that allow to model the topology, geometry and physical properties of geological objects in a unified way, while considering all kinds of data related to these objects. The modeling process thus allows the simplified representation of geological objects. The assembly of these simplifications of real objects into a coherent and logical whole form the geological model. Geologists have always sought to visualize geological objects in three dimensions and to understand the relationships between them and their three-dimensional environment because, in addition to providing a more realistic visualization of geology, 3D geological models can provide a better understanding and interpretation of geology by explicitly accessing the third dimension[18,21]. The objects to be represented can be geological units (lithological or stratigraphic), structural features (faults and fractures), fossil fuel reservoirs or mineral deposits, etc. Mineral deposits and reservoirs are objects commonly represented in geological models as geological units, which can be represented by their boundaries or volumes. Even if they do not correspond to geological objects, it is often necessary to represent boreholes because they provide direct and reliable data about the subsurface that are not otherwise accessible and are used to interpret the geology [27,30]. The primary objective of many geologic modeling projects is to find potential deposits and reservoirs to make exploration more efficient and rentable[18,36]. In addition, the 3D models and the digital tools used to build and manipulate these objects allow not only the simultaneous three-dimensional analysis of geological systems and their properties, but also certain quantitative studies of geological resources such as the estimation of precious metals. The different types of models in geology are essentially analogues, conceptual models, behavioral models and geomodels. An analogue is a typical example considered representative of a certain family of objects. It is usually a well-documented case study, often chosen among structures outcropping at the surface, allowing direct and precise analyses that would be impossible to perform on an object at depth [14]we then speak of a field analogue. The analogue is therefore a simplification of the object or family of objects studied. Since each case is unique, the analogue and the object represented are never exactly the same[3]. Another simplification is implicitly achieved when an analogue is under different conditions than the object under study if it is at the surface while the object under study is at depth, which may alter some of its properties. The conceptual model, on the other hand, is a view of mind that brings together a group of observable features and their interpretation[9]. It generally relies on analogues to illustrate its main characteristics. The behavioral model defined here is a sophisticated form of conceptual model characterized by a quantitative aspect in the form of equations or diagrams representing the response of an object or the evolution of its characteristics, following certain solicitations[6,16]. These models can be derived from mathematical abstractions or from empirical studies. Some of their parameters may depend on characteristics, such as the type of rock studied. The geomodel is a model or prototype that represents a particular geological object. It can use an analog or digital medium; in both cases, it represents a certain simplification linked to its scale and resolution. It is used to collect information and its interpretations to verify its consistency and simulate the behavior of the modeled object; the final goal is usually to study the behavior of the object in real size to prepare for exploitation[14]. This type of model is called a geomodel or quantitative model because it is generally used to provide a quantified answer to a question of interest. Its quantitative aspect primarily involves calibration to available data, which distinguishes it from conceptual models[3]. The geomodel also allows for data reconciliation. Indeed, it makes it possible to consider redundancies and contradictions between the different information. The confrontation of the conceptual models with the data gives the geomodels a predictive character, which can be verified by comparing the predictions made with the

site data[32]. In the mining context, building a quantitative model is a key step in integrating all available information to simulate the directions of mineralization during mining[25]. It also serves as a support for calculations that allow the evaluation of ore volumes, grades and density of the different blocks from the data using geostatistical approaches or by simulating the formation of the resource. The latter type of model will be used for this work.

Three-dimensional representation is of prime importance in the mining industry given the large amounts invested during the exploration phases. Indeed, at the end of the last century, several mining companies had to abandon their projects because of an erroneous approach during the realization of the model, which led to an overestimation of the resources in their exploitation permits[8]. Since then, the reliability of the model and the resource estimate is a very important step after the drilling campaigns to reduce the financial risks and optimize the return for the mining companies. The mineral resource to be estimated can be defined as a concentration of material naturally present in the earth's crust in solid form and in such quantity that its extraction for economic purposes is actually or potentially feasible [32]. They are classified according to a number of criteria including, but not limited to, the quality and reliability of drilling and sampling data, the presence of reverse circulation, diamond drilling, and/or production drilling, the distance between sampling points (drill density), the continuity of geological structures and the continuity of grades within those structures, variographic patterns and associated ranges (primary and secondary structures), and the level of confidence of the geological interpretation. Based on these criteria, resources are subdivided in increasing order of geological confidence into inferred, indicated and measured resources[13]. The objective of this study is to model the mineralization of the ore zones in both the oxidized and the sulphide, and then to estimate the resources of this prospect. The in-place resources will be estimated by applying the geostatistical method of inverse weighting which will be verified by the nearest neighbor method applied to the block model.

Geological setting

The exploration permit for this study is located in Côte d'Ivoire in the Baoulé-Mossi area, more precisely in the Yaoure unit east of the town of Bouafle (Figure 1). It belongs to Exploration Permit 397, in the Yaoure mountains, located 300 km from Abidjan (economic capital of Côte d'Ivoire) and 50 km from Yamoussoukro (political capital).

Fig. 1: Location of the study area

This geological unit is located in a series of tholeiitic basic volcanics and acid volcanics associated with volcano-sedimentary units. These units contain numerous intrusions of basic to ultrabasic plutonic rocks and some intermediate rocks such as granodiorites. The geology of the permit and the study area is illustrated in Figure 2.

Fig. 2: Simplified geological map of the Yaoure gold project exploration permit

According to the work of Tempier [30], Fabre [11], the lithostratigraphy of the Yaoure Mountains complex is presented from bottom to top as follows

- a set of migmatic gneisses with biotites marked by a tight centimetric foliation that can attenuate and disappear in places to give the rock the appearance of a homogeneous granite. These gneisses occur only at the western end of the Yaoure and correspond to a catazonal structural level;
- a sedimentary ensemble made up of a dark green silty-clay material changing to fine grauwacke sandstones sometimes enriched in quartz levels. These sequences have a metric amplitude with a millimetric bedding. The stratification is generally transposed in the plane of the schistosity and the synchronous metamorphism of this deformation is of green schist type;
- an essentially volcanic ensemble made up of pillow-like andesitic basalt flows associated with thin levels of epiclasts and hyaloclasts.

Late plutonic intrusions of gabbros, ultrabasites, diorites, dykes, rhyolites-dacites and unconformable granites would mark the end of regional magmatism.

Materials and methods

1. Material

The modeling and estimation of the mineral resources of the CMA-North prospect required the use of a database consisting of different tables obtained from mining drillings (reverse circulation and diamond drilling).

1.1. Data base

The drilling database was provided in Excel files. A total of one hundred and seventy-nine drill holes, including seventy-six diamond drill holes and forty-three reverse circulation holes were used for the estimation. The tables used for this exercise included information on the identity of the drill holes, the direction and dip of the drill holes, the different gold grades, the density and the different lithologies crossed by the drill holes.

The borehole identity table controls the database and allows tracking of borehole information in an organized manner. The borehole identity is the main element that links all the information in the different tables together. The borehole identity table must contain the borehole identity (BHID), X (UTM_EASTING), Y (UTM_NORTHING) and Z (UTM_RL) coordinates, borehole depth (TOTAL DEPHT), direction (AZIMUT) and the inclination (DIP) programmed for the survey and optionally other information.

The table for monitoring the direction and dip of the boreholes makes it possible to follow the actual evolution of the borehole as a function of depth, considering the Azimuth and the plunge of the core axis. The measurement of the borehole deviation is done sequentially at specific distances or by interval. The fields of this table are made up of the hole identity (BHID), the depth of the measurement (DEPTH), the hole inclination (DIP) and the Azimuth.

The gold grade table is used to evaluate the mineralized zones. This is the table that contains the gold grades. These data are linked to the sampling data and the assay laboratory results. The table includes the hole identity (BHID), the "From-To" interval, the sample number (SAMPLE_ID) and the gold grade (Au_ppm) of the sample.

The lithology table is used to graphically represent the various subsurface layers and their thickness. To facilitate data manipulation, a lithology code (text and/or numbers), which is a short version of the lithology description, is usually developed. This table includes the hole identity (BHID), the "From-To" interval and the lithology code (LITHOCODE) assigned to the interval.

The density table contains density data. It is used to determine the tonnage of the material and to estimate the quantity of metal in place. The selection of density samples is done by the geologist posted on the drill site according to a certain number of criteria, then transferred to the laboratory which determines the value of the density. This table includes the hole identity (BHID), the "From-To" interval of the sample and the density value (t/m³) and additional information.

1.2. Data processing software

For this work, several softwares were used. These are among others:

-**Microsoft Excel**: to analyze, correct if necessary and filter the data, in order to ensure their reliability and especially their consistency;

-**MapInfo Professional 14.0-Discover 2012**: was used to highlight the lithological model, the oxidized-sulfide limits as well as the gold contents on the studied sections;

- **Geovia Surpac 6.6.2**: for the realization, the visualization of the model and then for the estimation of the resources.

2. Methods

The methodology used in this study followed different steps that led to the construction of the 3D model and then to the estimation of the resources. The different steps for this work are summarized below:

Fig. 3: Workflow for modeling and resource estimation

2.1. Construction of the model

The construction of the 3D geomodel is a very important step for resource estimation. Indeed, it requires that all the specific geological variables are considered and integrated to build a valid domain model.

2.1.1. Data validation and structuring

This is a preliminary step before carrying out any operation. Indeed, before using the data from the drillings, it is necessary to carry out a succession of tasks of sorting, selection, formatting and structuring of the data in order to eliminate redundant and/or erroneous records; this ensures the coherence of the database and above all that it can be used effectively for the work.

2.1.2. Realization of the drilling sections

The first step in a modeling project is to establish a series of borehole sections from the data contained in the database tables. A section is a vertical cross-sectional representation of the boreholes drilled on a line. It is used to interpret the geological limits of the different rock types. It is also used to correlate, from one borehole to another, the different geological layers between them. In addition to this aspect, it also makes it possible to define the boundary between oxidized and sulphidized ore. The mineralized structures (represented in our case by quartz veins) are also represented for each hole at the depths at which they were measured. The 119 holes drilled were divided into a total of 11 sections. These sections follow an east-west orientation and are separated by fifty meters. On the x-axis, the coordinates are UTM_Easting and on the y-axis UTM_Northing. Figure 4 shows the layout and distribution of these drill holes on the prospect and on each section.

Fig. 4: Map showing the location of the different drilled wells

2.1.3. Digitalization of the interest zones

The next step is to describe the grade envelopes using a gold cut-off grade of 0.4 g/t for both the oxidized and the sulphide ore. The red areas represent grades greater than or equal to 0.4 g/t (Figure 5). Both grade envelopes were interpreted on all eleven sections.

Digitizing consists of delimiting the zones with gold contents greater than or equal to the cut-off grade and combining them into a single file. The files obtained after digitizing are "STRING" type files. These files are made up of a succession of three-dimensional coordinates that represent, in this case, grades greater than or equal to 0.4 g/t.

Fig. 5: Example of digitization of borehole section 777535N

2.1.4. Data triangularization and mineralization model

The oxidized and sulphide grade envelopes previously obtained on the different sections, allow the generation of Digital Terrain Model (DTM) files by the triangularization process. The DTMs obtained are a set of triangles representing the surfaces occupied by the mineralization. This step constitutes the first phase of the solid model. Wireframes which are a form of 3D solids are generated after having validated the DTMs obtained for the oxidized and the sulfide. An example of a message after validation is shown below.

Solid validation report									
Layer: fresh.dtm									
Object	Trisolation	Valid	Open/closed	Connected	Duplicate (removed)	Invalid Edges	Intersecting	Reversed	
1	1	Valid	Closed	Connected	0	0	0	0	
1	2	Valid	Closed	Connected	0	0	0	0	
1	3	Valid	Closed	Connected	0	0	0	0	
Totals					0	0	0	0	
Autocorrect audit results									
Object	Trisolation	Steps	Taken To Resolve						
Solid validation report						1/1			

Fig. 6 : Sulfide zone solid validation message

2.2. Resource estimation process

2.2.1. Statistical analysis of data

The resource estimate begins with a statistical analysis of the data in order to identify possible biases that could distort the estimate. Thus, certain statistical parameters of the table containing the gold grades are determined to characterize the numerical behavior (statistical distribution) of the grades (Figures 7 and 8).

Fig. 7: Histogram and statistical parameters of the crude grades of oxidized ore

The average raw data for the oxidized ore solid is 1.867 and the coefficient of variation is 2.778. The value of gold will have to be limited in order to avoid the nugget effect.

Fig. 8: Oxidized solid gold probability chart

From the above histogram and probability plot, the gold value was covered at 16.5g/t for the oxidized ore grades.

Fig. 9: Histogram and statistical parameters of crude sulfide ore grades chart

Note that for solid sulphide ore, the average and coefficient of variation of the line data are 2.940 g/t and 1.414 respectively.

Fig. 10: Solid gold sulfide probability chart

From these graphs, gold values were covered at 20g/t in the sulphide

2.2.2. Sampling length regularization and Capping

In this step, the length of the borehole samples is standardized. This is done to reduce the variability of the sampling intervals. The sample length of 1 m was used based on the dominant interval length of the raw samples. Next, capping, which consists of setting limits to avoid the nugget effect that could distort the results, was performed. This is based on the statistical analyses performed above.

2.2.3. Block model

The block model consists of a three-dimensional division of the mineralized envelope into several parts that are composed of interpolated values. Each block is assigned spatial coordinates, average grade, size and density based on fragmental knowledge of drilling information. Parameters such as volume, tonnage, average grade of its 3D blocks are estimated. The centroid of each block defined its geometric dimensions in each axis, i.e. its Y, X and Z coordinates. The variables used in the resource block include

autc_id	- id grade Au (g/t)
autc_nn	- nn grade Au (g/t)
ns_id	- number of samples used in the estimation
nh_id	- number of boreholes used for estimation
dist_id	- distance of the composites used for the estimation
avgdis_id	- average distance id
avgdis_nn	- average distance nn
den	- density (g/m ³)
Class	- Classification
	Measured= 1
	Indicated=2
	Inferred =3
	Unclassified = 4

2.2.4. Estimation of block grades

The grades of the different blocks were estimated as described above. Each block contains attributes for each of the modeled properties. The inverse distance weighting method was used to estimate the grades of the different blocks and the nearest neighbor method was used to verify them. These geostatistical methods consider the spatial variability of the grade and the difference in volume between the measurements and the blocks. The direction and inclination of the blocks were specified (N0° and N-60°) according to the orientation of the structures containing the mineralization. All blocks were estimated using a minimum of 6 and a maximum of 15 samples per block.

2.2.5. Resource classification

Measured resources are defined as resources with a sampling distance less than or equal to 25;

Indicated resources are defined as resources with a sampling distance greater than 25 and less than or equal to 50;

Inferred resources are defined as block estimates with a sampling distance greater than 50 m and less than or equal to 100 m. Unclassified material is defined as estimated blocks with a sampling distance greater than 100m. The table below summarizes the classification.

Measured	Indicated	Inferred	Unclassified
<= 25	>25 et <=50	>50 et <=100	>100

2.2.6. Validation of the estimation

It is important during the estimation process to validate the quality of the methods used because they are not automatically representative of reality. The model was validated after a check to ensure that all the blocks in the different domains (oxidized and sulfidized) were estimated.

Results and discussion

1. Results

1.1. Borehole profile study

On the CMA-North prospect, a correlation of one hundred and nineteen drill holes, distributed over the eleven sections, was carried out. This correlation highlighted two main lithological sets representing the two mineralized domains. An example is shown in Figure 11.

Fig. 11: Representation of the 777085 N drilling section

1.2. Mineralization model of the CMA-North prospect

The mineralization model of the CMA-Nord prospect has mainly a North-South orientation for both oxide and sulphide. It appears in a lenticular form, more visible with the sulphide and plunging towards the east.

Fig. 12: 3D model of the mineralization of the oxidized part

Fig. 13: 3D model of sulfide mineralization

The final mineralization model is obtained by superimposing the two obtained models.

Fig. 14: Mineralization model (Profile view)

1.3. Capping

Limits were determined by examining statistical analyses performed on all grade values. Based on the statistics, the oxide and sulphide grades were cut from 50 g/t to 16.5 g/t and from 50 g/t to 20 g/t respectively to avoid overestimation. The average oxide and sulphide grades decreased from 1.867 to 1.266 and from 2.940 to 1.269 respectively. The coefficient of variation also decreases from 2.778 to 2.131 for the oxide and from 1.414 to 1.014 for the sulfide. The histograms of the grades covered are shown in Figures 15 and 16.

Fig. 15: Histogram of the covered grades of the oxidized ore (16.5 g/t)

Figure 16: Histogram of covered grades of sulfide ore (20 g/t)

1.4. Block models

Each block was assigned spatial coordinates, size, density, and metal content based on point knowledge from the borehole data. A parent block size of 12mE by 12mN by 3mZ and a variable block size of 6mE by 6mN by 1.5mZ were selected for the blocks. The block model parameters are the same for both the sulfide and oxidized and are defined in all three dimensions. The limits are shown in the table below (Table 2).

Table-2: Parameters of the block model				
Axes	Start	End	Main block	Variable block
Easting (X)	221100	221650	12	6
Northing(Y)	777000	777570	12	6
Elevation (Z)	10	320	3	1,5

1.4. Densities

The average densities were estimated based on the density values of the individual samples and then interpolated into both the oxidized and the sulfide. The density parameters used in the block models are presented below (Table 3).

Table-3: Density of the block models		
Ore type	Total number of samples	Density (t/m³)
Oxide	183	1,89
Sulfide	2151	2,85

3.1.3. Estimation of the blocks

The ratio of total tonnage and estimated contents in the various solids is shown in Tables 4 and 5 below.

Table-4: Ratio for oxide ore solid			
Cut-off grade	Volume	Tonnage	Grades
0.2	2535938	7227423	1.063
0.4	2399575	6838788	1.260
1.0	990172.5	2821991	2.444
2.0	166437.5	474347	4.979
5.0	37612.5	107195	9.394

Table-5: Ratio for the solid of the sulfide ore			
Cut-off grade	Volume	Tonnage	Grades
0.2	1641513	3102459	1.199
0.4	1623138	3067730	1.240
1.0	1072000	2026080	2.231
2.0	942625	1781561	3.822
5.0	198750	375637	7.948

The results for the oxidized and sulfidized material are presented in the tables below for both methods used. The nearest neighbor method was used to verify the inverse distance method.

Table-6: Oxidized solid estimation using the two methods					
Inverse distance weighting			Nearest neighbor method		
Volume	Tonnage	Volume	Tonnage	Volume	Tonnage
1623138	3067730	1.24	1451888	2744068	1.03

Table-7: Sulphide solid estimation using the two methods					
Inverse distance weighting			Nearest neighbor method		
Volume	Tonnage	Volume	Tonnage	Volume	Tonnage
1623138	3067730	1.24	1451888	2744068	1.03

The difference in tonnage between the inverse distance weighting method and the nearest neighbor method is about 12% for oxide and 5% for sulfide. These differences are considered minimal and acceptable for this study.

3.1.4. Resource estimation

Resources were estimated and classified according to the constraints applied to the solid blocks. Resources were estimated using the 0.4 g/t cut-off grade imposed for this study; final block models were used for estimation and resources were calculated by material type (oxidized and sulfide).

Fig. 17: Classification of resources in the oxidized

Fig. 18: Classification of resources in the sulfide

The green and blue colors represent the indicated and inferred resources respectively. The red color represents the unestimated areas of these models.

The overall estimate based on the different cut-off grades gives the results shown in the tables. The tonnage and grade classifications for oxidized and sulphide ore are also presented.

Table-8: Oxidized solid @ 0.4g/t cut-off grade (1.0g/t nominal cut-off envelope)

Cutt-off Ores	Cut-off grade @ 0.2g/t		Cut-off grade @ 0.4g/t		Cut-off grade @ 1.0g/t		Cut-off grade @ 5.0g/t	
	Tonnage	Grade	Tonnage	Grade	Tonnage	Grade	Tonnage	Grade
Indicated	1551230	1.34	1012547	2.03	716151	3.53	410427	8.84
Inferred	2280310	0.81	1900136	1.86	1282929	2.74	593962	8.04
Grand Total	3831540	1.07	2912683	1.95	1999080	3.13	1004389	8.44

Table-9: Sulphide @ 0.4g/t cut-off grade (0.4g/t nominal cut-off envelope)

Cutt-off Ores	Cut-off grade @ 0.2g/t		Cut-off grade @ 0.4g/t		Cut-off grade @ 1.0g/t		Cut-off grade @ 5.0g/t	
	Tonnage	Grade	Tonnage	Grade	Tonnage	Grade	Tonnage	Grade
Indicated	2831913	1.09	2786429	1.76	627332	3.72	69796	9.54
Inferred	4395510	1.08	3626799	1.56	2194657	2.81	88150	9.02
Grand Total	7227423	1.08	6413228	1.66	2821990	3.26	157946	9.28

Discussion

The mineralization model of the CMA-North prospect shows a predominantly north-south orientation of the mineralization; moreover, the geometry of the mineralization shows that it is a lens-shaped mineralization plunging towards the east. Most of the resource is located at depth (fresh rock) and a small portion is located in the altered zone. Similar results were obtained by structural analysis and remote sensing by BRGM[4], Affian [1], Koffi[20]. Indeed, these authors used remote sensing and structural site analyses to show that the main directions of the structures in the were NS to NNE-SW with a dip of 40° to the east, and that most of the gold resources appeared to be at the hard rock level; Thus, modeling confirms that it has become a very important visualization and interpretation tool for decision making[7] at all scales of mineral exploration. However, several limitations arise from its realization and interpretation [9]. Indeed, the modeling process is characterized by pervasive uncertainty throughout the process[12,19]. This uncertainty is due to the fact that the model is not determined a priori, which opens up multiple possible interpretations of a given study area.

First, the ability to directly measure phenomena is a limiting factor in geologic modeling[24,34]. Indeed, it is difficult to completely and accurately measure mineralization because it is located below the Earth's surface and is not directly accessible. Therefore, the collected data are often scattered, limited with respect to the area to be modeled, and may have a heterogeneous spatial distribution[16,22].

Second, geoscience data sources are varied. Examples include borehole data, surface sampling, geochemical analyses, etc.[15]. Thus, for a single modeling project, one has a very large amount of heterogeneous data that is nevertheless sparse, given the usually large dimensions of the model. One must therefore integrate these data in a logical and coherent way in the same model and this represents a major difficulty in 3D geological modeling[32].

A final difficulty in 3D geological modeling is the diversity of model building procedures and the many steps to be followed. Indeed, there is no single method for building 3D geological models; the method of model construction depends directly on the available data, the type of environment to be modeled, and the purpose of the modeling[26]. Indeed, the modeling of a geological object is done in several steps and often requires a significant amount of work to process the basic data in order to build a quality model that corresponds to reality [23]. Some of these steps involved in building a model include: importing borehole data, cleaning the data, building surface objects and modifying them, building volume objects, etc. and involve decision making at each step to ensure that the final model is valid[17,35].

It should be noted that resource estimation techniques are of some complexity and require several approximations. Indeed, the values attributed to the unsampled areas can be very different from the reality of the subsurface[10,33] due to the complexity of the latter. This can lead to an overestimation of the resources. The results of the deterministic inverse distance and nearest neighbor weighting methods show an acceptable difference. The low coefficient of variation between the two deterministic methods is explained by the fact that these methods have in common that they only consider the distance between points, which is why they are often used together [2,3]; this gives more weight to the data groupings, although this is not necessarily justified.

Conclusion

At the end of our work, whose main objective was to model the gold mineralization of the CMA-North prospect and to estimate the mineral resources of this prospect, important results were obtained. The first step consisted in structuring and processing the database to ensure its consistency. Next, a series of cross-sections of the drill holes was carried out, which made it possible to determine the lithology and specially to delineate the ore zones (oxidized and sulphide)

according to the cut-off grade. Finally, the construction of wireframes by digitizing and triangularizing the zones of importance allowed the establishment of the mineralization model. This model shows that the mineralization has a north-south extension and a large thickness of the envelope of the sulphide mineralization compared to the oxide mineralization. The block model was then used to estimate the mineral resources. The geostatistical method of inverse weighting was applied to this block model and verified by comparison with the nearest neighbor method. The results of the estimation revealed that on the CMA-North prospect, the mineralization is mainly in the sulphide zone and a small amount in the altered rock.

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